

**Deliverable
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1
FINAL VERSION**

**Data Management Plan
FINAL VERSION**

**Workpackage 1 of
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES**

Responsible Partner: SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JRP/JIP Report	Data Management Plan
Join Research / Integrative Project	JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES
JRP/JIP Leader	Pikka Jokelainen, SSI
Other contributors	TOXOSOURCES Consortium
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):.....</p>

D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

FINAL VERSION

Background

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

(<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/>)

TOXOSOURCES is a 3-year Joint Research Project of the One Health EJP that focuses on *Toxoplasma gondii* at the interface of humans, animals, food, and environment. TOXOSOURCES Consortium comprises 21 One Health EJP partners and several external partners.

Project Leader and DMP contact person: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, PIJO@ssi.dk

Work Package:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1 Coordination and impact

Task:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1-T1 Management, coordination and communication

Aim and focus, specific considerations

Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of data management during a project. It covers the life cycle of the data from collection to availability and storage. DMP of TOXOSOURCES was a living document that included the relevant categories and aspects of the types of data generated, collected and collated during the project.

Process and format

The TOXOSOURCES DMP was compiled using a specific tool provided by the OHEJP: Collaborative Data Platform (DCP). At the time of preparing the first version of the DMP and related deliverable, the CDP tool was not yet available, but data types and specific considerations were listed.

The list of data categories covered in TOXOSOURCES DMP was specified and updated during the project, and management of the data was discussed proactively. Ethical considerations, GDPR, data security and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) were considered and discussed along the process.

Resources

TOXOSOURCES Project Leader is responsible of the TOXOSOURCES DMP. Time for developing and maintaining the DMP was specifically allocated in the workplan. TOXOSOURCES Project Leader participates also in the DMP Committee of the One Health EJP, and was involved in preparing guidance and evaluation of DMPs within the One Health EJP.

TOXOSOURCES DMP was regularly discussed with the TOXOSOURCES Work Package leaders and with the TOXOSOURCES Consortium during the project. Resources were earmarked for dissemination during the project in 2020-2022, and for publishing Gold open access during the project duration 2020-2022 as well as in January-September 2023.

Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable

TOXOSOURCES set ambitious aims to make the research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR-principle). The DMP work supported this.

The data are being published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and have been very actively disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events. Specific repositories and data types are used as suitable.

In addition to the components of the FAIR-principle, transparency and visibility were also emphasized. The deliverables were used for transparency: reporting the step-by-step approaches and progress of the work. The information was made available in a timely manner: all (100%) Deliverables were submitted by their deadlines. Moreover, linking with the One Health Outcome Inventory (OHOI: <https://onehealthejp.eu/outcome-inventory/>) was actively utilized. The OHOI is a public database of

scientific and integrative outcomes from One Health EJP that lists databases, strain collections, tools and other scientific output and facilitates communication by providing contact information. Visibility was supported by focus on dissemination: both progress and results were disseminated to target audiences, including scientific audiences and stakeholders.

The publishing of scientific articles continues in January to September 2023: all generated, collected and collated data will be publicly available at the end of September 2023.

All outputs from the project are made available on the project website:

<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/>

The related data are continuously made available in connection to Deliverables and scientific publications, and are easily findable via Zenodo using the keyword "TOXOSOURCES" as search term:

https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22TOXOSOURCES%22&sort=publication_date

As the project is about One Health, inter-disciplinary interoperability and findability were considered important. We focused on keywords, signposting and cross-linking to support findability across the different fields. Uploading all key outputs to Zenodo and using the project name 'TOXOSOURCES' as keyword proved useful - it was easy to guide colleagues to find more information.

We also used 'One Health' as a keyword, to emphasize the One Health focus of the project. Discussions on this contributed to the idea of a case study on using 'One Health' as a keyword, which became a co-authored publication (Benedetti et al. 2022). The experiences from TOXOSOURCES thereby contributed to "discussions about One Health, FAIRness, cross-sectoral research collaborations and science-to-policy translation" - and exemplify what became recommended based on the case study: "signposting to indicate that a given publication is relevant for One Health".

Benedetti, G., Jokelainen, P., & Ethelberg, S. (2022). Search term "One Health" remains of limited use to identify relevant scientific publications: Denmark as a case study. *Frontiers in public health*, 10, 938460. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.938460>
<https://zenodo.org/record/6951259#.Y7CYGHbMKUK>

Reflections and self-assessment

Working on DMP continuously during the project lifetime was beneficial. It supported the collection of the data, management of the collected and collated data, dissemination of the data, as well as optimising the data for further usability. Making data available and findable helps to maximise impact of the work done. Overall our experience of the DMP work is positive, and we have been happy to share our experiences with other projects.

Dataset ID	Category	Type of data	Description of data	Contact	Dissemination	Official Referencing	Open access	Ethical Aspects	Keywords	Format
JRP-22-DATA-FROM-LITERATURE-REVIEWS	Research data	Data collection	Data from literature reviews performed during TOXOSOURCES	pijo@ssi.dk	The data are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Based on existing literature	pathogen; prevalence; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	Excel, PDF
JRP-22-QUESTIONNAIRE-RESULTS	Research data	Questionnaires	Questionnaire results	pijo@ssi.dk	The data are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Aggregated, anonymized responses	questionnaire; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	PDF
JRP-22-EXPOSURE-SURVEY-DATA	Research data	Datasets/Data bases	Data from multicentre exposure survey conducted in TOXOSOURCES	pijo@ssi.dk	The data are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Aggregated, anonymized responses	pathogn; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	PDF

JRP-22-SOPS-GUIDELINES	Methodologies	Methods	SOPs and guidelines created during TOXOSOURCES	pijo@ssi.dk	The SOPs and guidelines are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Building on previous work, transparency: the step-by-step processes described in articles and/or deliverables.	method; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	PDF
JRP-22-METADATA-ISOLATES	Research data	Biological collection	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> isolates	pijo@ssi.dk	The relevant metadata are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Selection of available existing strains were cultivated in vitro during TOXOSOURCES. The key reference strains are cultivated at numerous laboratories and available from collections.	pathogen; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	isolates
JRP-22-SEQUENCES	Research data	Molecular collection	Sequences of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> created during TOXOSOURCES	pijo@ssi.dk	The sequences are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and related results are actively disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	WGS of a selection of existing strains.	WGS; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	sequence data

JRP-22-RING-TRIAL-RESULTS	Research data	Data collection	Results of ring trials conducted during TOXOSOURCES	pijo@ssi.dk	The results are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Aggregated data, identity of laboratories not shown	method; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	PDF
JRP-22-MODELS	Methodologies	Methods	Models developed and optimised during TOXOSOURCES	pijo@ssi.dk	The models are published in connection to open access scientific articles and/or public project deliverables, and disseminated to scientific audiences at scientific events	The articles and deliverables are available via project website and via zenodo.	Yes	Models	method; model; Toxoplasma gondii; TOXOSOURCES	

Key links

<https://onehealthjp.eu/jrp-toxosources/>

https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22TOXOSOURCES%22&sort=publication_date

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